

WG5 Deliverable 1 – Citizen-science ontology

Date: September 13, 2018

Participants: Luigi Ceccaroni, Sven Schade, Lucy Bastin, Chrisa Tsinaraki, Rob Lemmens, Gilles Falquet, Friederike Klan, Jaume Piera, Jakub Trojan, Imre Lendak, Vyron Antoniou, Mirjana Žabić, Joan Masó, Maria Antonia Brovelli, Frank Ostermann, Marco Minghini, Maryam Lotfian, Gloria Bordogna, Santiago De La Riva

Background

The main aim of COST Action CA15212 “**Citizen Science to promote creativity, scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe**” (2016-2020) [[https:// www.cs-eu.net/](https://www.cs-eu.net/)] is to bundle capacities across Europe to investigate and extend the impact of the scientific, educational, policy, and civic outcomes of citizen science with the stakeholders from all sectors concerned (e.g., policy makers, social innovators, citizens, cultural organizations, researchers, charities and NGOs), to gauge the potential of citizen science as enabler of social innovation and socio-ecological transition.

One goal of the COST Action is to help create an ontology (including a vocabulary) for describing citizen-science projects, observations and analyses, building upon prior research and existing standards, which any organization can model their database structure upon. This goal is also linked to the larger objectives of the international Data and Metadata Working Group of the Citizen Science Association (CSA) and the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA).

Objectives

The general objectives of *working group 5* (WG5) “**Improve data standardization and interoperability**” are:

- to explore ways for integrating data and knowledge related to citizen-science initiatives and suggest mechanisms for standardization, interoperability, and quality control;
- to improve the technical foundations to foster the impact of citizen science globally.

A WG5’s specific objective is to help develop an ontology of citizen-science projects (including a vocabulary of concepts and metadata) to support data sharing among citizen-science projects. WG5 coordinated with activities on data and service interoperability carried out in Europe, Australia and the USA (e.g., the CSA’s international Data and Metadata Working Group [<http://www.citizenscience.org/association/about/working-groups/data-and-metadata-working-group/>]), and took into account existing standards.

Scope of this deliverable

This document follows the Geneva Declaration on Citizen Science Data and Metadata Standards that emerged from the [COST Action WG5 workshop in Geneva \(Switzerland\), 6th of June 2018](#). It proposes an **ontology of citizen science** in the form of changes and extensions to the PPSR Core model (Version 1) as presented in the [Citizen Science Association Data & Metadata Working Group: Report from CSA 2017 and Future Outlook](#).

In its current form, this document introduces a proposal related only to central elements of the model, i.e. it contains important parts but not all of the changes envisaged by the [COST Action on Citizen Science](#). We followed this approach in order to initiate important discussions and preparations of a next version of the **PPSR Core Conceptual Model (CCM)**.

Notes on terminology

Classes and properties

In this document, we use a terminology typical of the ontology domain/community, which can be easily replaced (if needed) by another terminology, more typical of another domain/community. We use “class” or “concept” to refer to what can be otherwise described as “entity”, and “property” to refer to what can be otherwise described as “relationship”. As in an ontology-oriented language, such as [OWL 2](#), a property usually originates from a “domain class” and points to a “range class” (i.e., a property connects a “domain class” to a “range class”), and a class can be specialised into “subclasses”. Thus, in the diagram below, "Project" is a domain class for the property "hasStartDate", and "StartDate" is a range class for this property. (Database terms and data types will only be specified once the model has been agreed. This will lead to updates in the tables that are currently presented in the 2017 version of PPSR-Core.)

The concepts of the *proposed PPSR CCM* are inspired by but not formally connected to other ontologies. Therefore, the *proposed PPSR CCM* does not commit to other ontologies’ semantics and does not inherit anything from other ontologies. For explicit connections with other ontologies, we recommend using *simple knowledge organization system (SKOS)* matches.

Rationale

The 2017 version of PPSR-Core includes a set of fields (see the figure below for a partial list).

PPSR-Core field name	PPSR-Core database term	Required	Data type	Multiplicity	Related standard/term mapping	Description/comments
Database information						
GUID	projectId	Y	text	1		Globally unique identifier (GUID) for the project; system generated.
External Id	projectExternalId	N	text	0:1		The identifier of the project in an external database or repository.
Origin	projectOriginalRepository	Y	text	1		The name of the project database where a project was first registered. Allows traceability of a project in multiple databases to its original registration.
Date Created	projectDateCreated	Y	dateTime	1	dcterms:created ISO 8601:2004 (E)	The date and time that the record was created in the database.
Date Updated	projectLast UpdatedDate	Y	dateTime	1	dcterms:modified ISO 8601:2004 (E)	The date and time that the record was last updated in the database.

Basic Project Information						
Name	projectName	Y	text	1	proj:name	Short name or title of the project.
Aim	projectAim	Y	text	1	proj:objective	Primary aim, goal, or objective.
Description	projectDescription	Y	text	1	rdfs:comment	Abstract or description of the project.
Tags	projectTags	N	vocabulary	0:many		Controlled vocabulary terms, supplied by the person who entered the project, to assist with search and filtering.
Keywords	dcat:keyword	N	text	0:many	dcat:keyword	Keywords (comma separated) which are indexed and aid in searching for and finding projects. Data Catalogue Vocabulary (DCAT)
Status	projectStatus	Y	vocabulary	1		The activity status of the project.
State date	projectStartDate	Y	dateTime	1	prov:startedAtTime ISO 8601:2004 (E)	The actual date that a project began.
End date	projectEndDate	N	dateTime	0:1	prov:endedAtTime ISO 8601:2004(E)	The actual date that a project ended.
Project topic	projectScienceType	N	vocabulary	0:many	proj: hasFieldOfResearch	The project topic or field of science.
Intended outcomes	project IntendedOutcomes	N	vocabulary	0:many	proj:objective	A project's goals, or intended outcomes of participation.
Images and communications						
Image	projectImage	N	image	0:1	foaf:img	An image to represent a project
Image credit	projectImage Credit	N	text	0:1		A credit for the image used to represent a project.
URL	projectUrl	N	http uri	0:1		URL to an external web site for the project.

These fields represent properties such as “projectDateCreated”. Those properties refer to concepts, which are not explicitly represented yet, i.e. they do not appear in the field list. For example, in the tables above, “projectURL” represents a property of a project, but the concept “Project” is not explicitly represented in the model. Likewise, “projectDateCreated” is a property of a project record, but the concept “Project Record” is not explicitly represented in the model.

These concepts are therefore not explicitly related to each other in the original model (see figure below).

As a first change, therefore, we propose (1) to add these implicit concepts as classes to the model, which in effect equate to the domain classes of the properties of the 2017 model; and (2) to add a formal representation of all corresponding properties (see an example in the figure below).

We use the following colour coding of graphical elements:

Additionally, we enriched the model connecting the various classes and adding new classes and properties, which are necessary to represent a basic description of projects and datasets (see examples in the figures below). In the rest of the document, a formal, complete description of a first set of suggested changes is provided. As mentioned earlier, the following ones are not all the changes envisaged by the COST Action.

Description of proposed changes

The object of this document is **one single** ontology, whose classes are all (directly or indirectly) connected. For clarity, its description is presented in the form of modules. Each module contains concepts that are grouped because of their close logical relationships. (This grouping is also referred to as “profiles”.) At the end of each module, a table with the included properties is presented. At the end of the document, a table with all the properties is presented. This duplication is just to facilitate the reading of the document.

Project core

The following figure represents the central class Project and its properties.

Proposed changes:

- Re-grouping (see figure below)
 - From “Image and communication”
 - From “Database information”
- Name changes
 - Concatenations (no free spaces)
 - “Project topic” to “Topic” (for matters of consistency)
- Additions
 - Duration (derived)

Basic Project Information						
Name	projectName	Y	text	1	proj:name	Short name or title of the project.
Aim	projectAim	Y	text	1	proj:objective	Primary aim, goal, or objective.
Description	projectDescription	Y	text	1	rdfs:comment	Abstract or description of the project.
Tags	projectTags	N	vocabulary	0:many		Controlled vocabulary terms, supplied by the person who entered the project, to assist with search and filtering.
Keywords	dcat:keyword	N	text	0:many	dcat:keyword	Keywords (comma separated) which are indexed and aid in searching for and finding projects. Data Catalogue Vocabulary (DCAT)
Status	projectStatus	Y	vocabulary	1		The activity status of the project.
State date	projectStartDate	Y	dateTime	1	prov:startedAtTime ISO 8601-2004 (F)	The actual date that a project began.
End date	projectEndDate	N	dateTime	0:1	prov:endedAtTime ISO 8601-2004(F)	The actual date that a project ended.
Project topic	projectScienceType	N	vocabulary	0:many	proj: hasFieldOfResearch	The project topic or field of science.
Intended outcomes	project IntendedOutcomes	N	vocabulary	0:many	proj:objective	A project's goals, or intended outcomes of participation.
Images and communications						
URL	projectUrl	N	http uri	0:1		URL to an external web site for the project.
Database information						
GUID	projectId	Y	text	1		Globally unique identifier (GUID) for the project; system generated.

Argumentation: “Duration” has been added because sometimes we only know the duration of a project but not the end date or the start date, so we need this option. For example, a project can have a duration of 36 months, but its starting date has not been defined yet. A web page is an essential part of most projects, and we suggest it to be part of the core. (This is just a presentation change; it does not change the semantics.) The edges between Duration, StartDate and EndDate show that the duration of a project can be computed from its start and end dates (if they are known). The status of a project is influenced by the start and end dates (in the sense that, depending on the start and end dates, the project status can be set to “non active” or “active”). For example, if we are in August 2018, the start date is January 2019 and the end date is December 2021, the status is “non active”.

Property	Description/comments
hasDescription	It associates a project to its textual description.
hasDuration	It associates a project to its duration.
hasEndDate	It associates a project to its end date.
hasIdentifier	It associates a project to its <i>Globally Unique Identifier</i> (GUID).
hasName	It associates a project to its name.
hasStartDate	It associates a project to its start date.
hasStatus	It associates a project to its activity status.
hasWebPage	It associates a project to its web page or URL.

Project detailed information

The following figure represents the central class Project and its properties related to the representation of the detailed information about the project. The two modules/profiles “Project core” and “Project detailed information” cover (and extend) “PPSR: Basic Project Information” in the 2017 model.

Proposed changes:

- Re-grouping (see figure below)
- Name changes
 - Plural to singular (for matters of consistency)
- Additions
 - Outcome

Basic Project Information						
Name	projectName	Y	text	1	proj:name	Short name or title of the project.
Aim	projectAim	Y	text	1	proj:objective	Primary aim, goal, or objective.
Description	projectDescription	Y	text	1	rdfs:comment	Abstract or description of the project.
Tags	projectTags	N	vocabulary	0:many		Controlled vocabulary terms, supplied by the person who entered the project, to assist with search and filtering.
Keywords	dcat:keyword	N	text	0:many	dcat:keyword	Keywords (comma separated) which are indexed and aid in searching for and finding projects. Data Catalogue Vocabulary (DCAT)
Status	projectStatus	Y	vocabulary	1		The activity status of the project.
State date	projectStartDate	Y	dateTime	1	prov:startedAtTime ISO 8601:2004 (F)	The actual date that a project began.
End date	projectEndDate	N	dateTime	0:1	prov:endedAtTime ISO 8601:2004(F)	The actual date that a project ended.
Project topic	projectScienceType	N	vocabulary	0:many	proj: hasFieldOfResearch	The project topic or field of science.
Intended outcomes	project IntendedOutcomes	N	vocabulary	0:many	proj:objective	A project's goals, or intended outcomes of participation.

Argumentation: “Outcome” has been added to allow representing the actual outcomes of a project, which are not necessarily the “intended outcomes”. The multiplicity of the properties related to “Outcome”, “Aim”, “IntendedOutcome” and, basically, to all classes of the model is “0..*”. Therefore, a project can have multiple outcomes, multiple keywords, multiple web pages and multiple names. In few occasions, such as “GUID”, multiplicity is better limited to “1”.

Property	Description/comments
hasAim	It associates a project to its aims.
hasKeyword	It associates a project to its keywords. Keywords are chosen from a predefined set of text expressions.
hasIntendedOutcome	It associates the intended outcomes of a project to its aims. For example, a project can have, as aim, “to evaluate impacts of citizen science” and, as intended outcome, “metrics and instruments to evaluate citizen science impacts”. As another example, a project can have, as aim, “to increase the impact of citizen science” and, as intended outcome, “an increase of the awareness of the citizens”.
hasOutcome	It associates a project to its outcomes.

hasTag	It associates a project to its tags. Tags are free text expressions. The keyword vocabulary can be used for tags.
--------	---

Project image

The following figure represents the central class Project and its properties to represent the images about the project and related to the project. The two modules/profiles “Project core” and “Project image” cover (and extend) “PPSR: Images and communications” in the 2017 model.

Proposed changes:

- Re-grouping (see figure below)
- Additions
 - Logo

Images and communications						
Image	projectImage	N	image	0:1	foaf:img	An image to represent a project
Image credit	projectImage Credit	N	text	0:1		A credit for the image used to represent a project
URL	projectUrl	N	http uri	0:1		URL to an external web site for the project.

Argumentation: A logo is a very common field in project catalogues and a characteristic of most projects.

Property	Description/comments
hasCredit	It associates an image to its credits.
hasImage	It associates a project to images about the project and related to the project.

Project record

A “ProjectRecord” class has been added to make the underlying structure explicit and to specify the semantics more formally. This concept does not refer to observations or to the dataset holding the project observations, but to a part of a database or spreadsheet that contains a complete set of information about the project. This is a concept that was implicit in the 2017 model, with a variety of characteristics that were well-defined, necessary and easily reusable. The project record, which is not essential to the representation of a project, given that all project metadata are defined and linked directly to the Project class, is basically used in catalogues and repositories of projects, such as Scistarter or BioCollect. Therefore, multiple project records can exist in different catalogues/repositories, which refer to the same project, and the “ProjectRecord” class helps the linkage among them. This class can also represent a snapshot of project information, which is used to make search and reasoning more efficient. The two modules/profiles “Project core” and “Project record” cover (and extend) “PPSR: Database information” in the 2017 model.

Proposed changes:

- Re-grouping (see figure below)
- Additions
 - Language
 - GUID (now also for the ProjectRecord)

Database information						
GUID	projectId	Y	text	1		Globally unique identifier (GUID) for the project; system generated.
External Id	projectExternalId	N	text	0:1		The identifier of the project in an external database or repository.
Origin	projectOriginalRepository	Y	text	1		The name of the project database where a project was first registered. Allows traceability of a project in multiple databases to its original registration.
Date Created	projectDateCreated	Y	dateTime	1	dcterms:created ISO 8601:2004 (E)	The date and time that the record was created in the database.
Date Updated	projectLastUpdatedDate	Y	dateTime	1	dcterms:modified ISO 8601:2004 (E)	The date and time that the record was last updated in the database.

Argumentation: The natural language of the project record is important because it can affect reuse and sharing. A GUID for the project record helps referencing the project through catalogues and repositories (good data management practice).

Property	Description/comments
describes	It associates the record with the project it refers to. In a concrete implementation, the link could be through the identifier "Project.GUID".
hasCreationDate	It associates the record with the date it was created.
hasExternalIdentifier	It associates the record with the identifier of a harvested or linked Project Record in another repository (see above). It promotes traceability.
hasIdentifier	It associates the record with its GUID (for example, identifier of a database record).
hasOrigin	It associates the record with an external source (if applicable) from which the record is derived - e.g. external catalogue from which it was harvested.
hasNaturalLanguage	It associates the record with a human-readable natural language in which it is written.
wasLastUpdated	It associates the record with the date it was last updated.

Project contact point

This concept is addressed in more detail as it is of importance for data management. The module “Project contact point” covers (and extends) “PPSR: Personal and Organizational Affiliates” in the 2017 model. At this stage, we only document a suggested re-modelling of “contact point”.

Proposed changes:

- Name changes
 - Generalizations (see figure below)
- Additions
 - Explicit conceptual type
 - Option for different ways of contacting

Personal and Organizational Affiliates						
Project host	projectResponsiblePartyName	Y	text	1	proj:hasLeader foaf:name prov:entity	Name of the primary organization responsible for hosting or implementing the project.
Project host contact	projectResponsiblePartyContact	N	text	0:1	proj:hasLeader foaf:{various}	The contact details for a party responsible for the project. This may include postal and street address, telephone and email details. Note that this is not parsed into individual properties.
Project host contact email	projectResponsiblePartyEmail	N	text	1		Email address for the person responsible for keeping the record up to date.
Project contact	projectContactName	N	text	1	proj:hasLeader Foaf:name prov:entity	The name of the person responsible for keeping the project up to date. Traditionally the primary project coordinator.
Project contact email	projectContactEmail	N	text	1	proj:hasLeader foaf:mbox	Email address for the person responsible for keeping the record up to date.
Associated organisation	projectAssociatedPartyName	N	text	0:many	proj:activityParticipationAssociation prov:agent rdfs:label	Short text name or title of a party (eg. Organisation) associated with the project and performing a role in the project.

Argumentation: We introduce ContactPointType as a simple way of separating contacts that serve different purposes. This modelling approach, which we borrowed from schema.org, avoids unnecessary sub-classing. Specific contact types can be specified using controlled vocabularies (see examples in the diagram). We use “MeansOfContact” to be able to specify email, phone, etc.

Property	Description/comments
hasContactPoint	It associates a project with an agent that acts as contact point for it.
hasContactDetails	It associates a contact point with its contact details.
hasMeansofContact	It associates a contact point with the applicable means of contact.
hasContactPointType	It associates a contact point with its type.

The concept “ContactPoint” could be used more widely, i.e. not only for Project contact points. It could, for example, also be re-used for a “ProjectRecord” (as suggested in the figure below), data sets and organisations.

Project funding

The module “Project funding” covers (and extends) “PPSR: Country specific terms” in the 2017 model.

Proposed changes:

- Name changes
 - Concatenations
 - Deletion of “FundingProgram” in property names (see figure below)
- Additions
 - Separation of the property “USFederalSponsor” into two more generic properties of the class “FundingSource” (“Name” and “FundingSourceType”)

Country specific terms						
US Federal sponsor	project UsFederalSponsor	N	vocabulary	0:many		Name of U.S. federal agency offering a project direct sponsorship, funding, or other support.
Funding Programme Description	programDescription	N	text	0:1		General description/summary of the Research Program or funding initiative.
Funding Programme ID	programId	N	text	0:1		The identifier of the initiative (e.g., overarching research program or funding initiative) encompassing the project
Funding Programme Name	programName	N	text	0:1		The initiative (e.g., overarching research program) encompassing the project (e.g., Horizon 2020)

Argumentation: Adding “FundingSource”, the model has a more robust structure that holds beyond US federal sponsoring. Added EU and US examples for illustration.

Property	Description/comments
hasDescription	It associates a funding program to its textual description.
hasFundingProgram	It associates a project to its funding program.
hasFundingSource	It associates a funding program to its funding source(s).
hasIdentifier	It associates a funding program to its GUID.
hasName	It associates a funding program / funding source to its name.
hasFundingSourceType	It associates a funding source with its type.

Project geography

Location and place information can be highly ambiguous. We defined a richer formal specification of the semantics of the terms used in order to avoid misinterpretations. We separated a project’s “GeographicExtent” from its “SpatialAreaOfInterest”. The former can be used to represent the partners or participants locations, whereas the latter is the area on which the project operates. As this might be out in space, we speak about “SpatialAreaOfInterest”

(i.e., not necessarily geography). This is not necessarily an “area”; it could be a “volume” (e.g. some part of our galaxy) and might be revised in the future. We could also add a “temporal extent of interest” (e.g. the 16th century) for historical projects.

The suggested structure might later also be re-used in other parts of the model.

Following the same principle as before (for contact point), we introduce possible separations of different types of administrative units. Each “AdministrativeUnit” can then have a name, a type and a code.

We use a common way of modelling geometric representations of spatial objects. We particularly account for point geometries (for the time being with two standard coordinates) and for polygon geometries, which have a point in their centre.

Following this approach, we started structuring spatial representations of multiple aspects of projects. This provides a considerably more precise extension to the 2017 PPSR model and opens the possibilities for more detailed extension in the future - if required by the community. The module “Project geography” covers (and extends – a lot) “PPSR: Geography” in the 2017 model.

In the figure below the relation between the 2017 model and the current proposal is explained.

Geography							
Project Latitude	projectPinLatitude	Y	floating point	1	GeoAPI:OGC:G2:SP2	Latitude coordinate of the center of the project area. Typically this is where the project is hosted, e.g., a home institution.	Project hasGeographicExtent GeographicExtent GeographicExtent hasGeometry Polygon Polygon hasCentroid Point Point hasLatitude Latitude Point hasLongitude Longitude
Project Longitude	projectPinLongitude	Y	floating point	1	GeoAPI:OGC:G2:SP2	Longitude coordinate of the center of the project area. Typically this is where the project is hosted, e.g., a home institution.	
Geographic extent	projectGeographicCoverage	N	GeoJSON, WKT, SHP	1	prop:hasAreaOfInterest GeoAPI:OGC:G2:SP2	User-defined geospatial representation of the project area footprint. Coverage is typically represented in a GeoJSON object which has a centroid coordinate ("center") and a definition of the boundary of the shape.	Project hasSpatialAreaOfInterest SpatialAreaOfInterest SpatialAreaOfInterest hasSpatialExtent SpatialExtent SpatialExtent hasGeometry Polygon
Project Geographic Coverage Centroid Latitude	projectGeographicCoverageCentroidLatitude	N	floating point	1	GeoAPI:OGC:G2:SP2	Latitude coordinate of the centroid of the project extent area. Latitude coordinate in geographic decimal degrees for the center or home base of the project best representing the project's location as a point.	Project hasSpatialAreaOfInterest SpatialAreaOfInterest SpatialAreaOfInterest hasSpatialExtent SpatialExtent SpatialExtent hasGeometry Polygon Polygon hasCentroid Point Point hasLatitude Latitude Point hasLongitude Longitude
Project Geographic Coverage Centroid Longitude	projectGeographicCoverageCentroidLongitude	N	floating point	1	GeoAPI:OGC:G2:SP2	Longitude coordinate of the centroid of the project extent area. Longitude coordinate in geographic decimal degrees for the center or home base of the project best representing the project's location as a point.	Project hasSpatialAreaOfInterest SpatialAreaOfInterest SpatialAreaOfInterest hasSpatialExtent AdministrativeUnit AdministrativeUnit hasAdministrativeUnitType AdministrativeUnitType AdministrativeUnitType = UNRegions
UN regions	unRegions	Y	vocabulary	1 many	Modified MSB coding classification	Select list of United Nations regions. Used for enabling regionalized views of projects in order to make searchability and applicability of projects more regionally relevant for users.	Project hasGeographicExtent GeographicExtent GeographicExtent hasName Name
Project location	projectLocality	N	text	0..1		Free text location specification.	

Property	Description/comments
contains	It associates a spatial extent with its sub-extends.
hasCentroid	It associates a polygon with its centroid.
hasCode	It associates an administrative unit with its code.

hasGeographicExtent	It associates a project with its geographic extent.
hasGeometry	It associates a spatial extent with its geometry.
hasLatitude	It associates a point with its latitude.
hasLongitude	It associates a point with its longitude.
hasName	It associates a spatial extent with its name.
hasSpatialAreaofInterest	It associates a project with its spatial area of interest.
hasSpatialExtent	It associates a spatial area of interest with its spatial extent.
hasAdministrativeUnitType	It associates an administrative unit with its type.

Next steps

The ones above are the most important elements of our proposed evolution of the PPSR CCM. However, the COST Action work covered many additional aspects and possible extensions, which are not included here.

This document represents the delivery, by COST Action’s WG5, of a formal proposal for a citizen-science ontology, with part of its latest results.

The CSA international WG on Citizen Science Data and Metadata is invited to discuss the alignment of the next version of the *project metadata model* (PMM) and the *dataset metadata model* (DMM) to the proposal of COST Action’s WG5.

Annex 1: summary of changes with respect to PPSR-Core (2017)

In the document, the original tables of the 2017 version of the model have been used to explain what would change according to this proposal in each of what has been called profile or module. In the following annex, a summary of all proposed changes is presented.

Resources

Latest version available at [<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1peRcL-UD0ZzDSIDI0TFR23p83sBi0AZoTeNaNHJfv-o/edit?usp=sharing>] (document); [https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ZkFBQhgxYuPN2aCg6pkG5S_9y6gp32dueOBdLjC9ns0/edit?usp=sharing] (annex) and [<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1PpngwK9d1WqSbil5UO81z19G-HibjnB6>] (graphical model).

Annex 1: summary of changes with respect to PPSR-Core (2017)

Notes

In this annex, a list of all proposed changes to PPSR Core Conceptual Model (CCM) is presented. Two tables are presented: the first one includes all the properties and the second one all the classes. With PPSR CCM V1, we mean the 2017 version; with PPSR CCM V2, we mean the COST Action version.

Multiplicity

Multiplicity	Option	Cardinality
0..1		No instances or one instance
1..1	1	Exactly one instance
0..*	*	Zero or more instances
1..*		At least one instance
m..n		At least m but no more than n instances

Datatypes

In a number of places in this document, we will see the notion of range for specifying a range of data values. The following built-in types of data range are used in OWL 2 and are reused here.

Built-in Datatypes

Universal Datatype	rdfs:Literal			
Numbers	owl:rational		owl:real	
	xsd:double	xsd:float	xsd:decimal	xsd:integer
	xsd:long	xsd:int	xsd:short	xsd:byte
	xsd:nonNegativeInteger		xsd:nonPositiveInteger	
	xsd:positiveInteger		xsd:negativeInteger	
	xsd:unsignedLong		xsd:unsignedInt	
	xsd:unsignedShort		xsd:unsignedByte	
	Strings	rdf:PlainLiteral (RDF plain literals)		
xsd:string		xsd:NCName	xsd:Name	xsd:NMTOKEN
xsd:token		xsd:language	xsd:normalizedString	
Boolean Values	xsd:boolean (value space: <i>true</i> and <i>false</i>)			
Binary Data	xsd:base64Binary		xsd:hexBinary	
IRIs	xsd:anyURI			
Time Instants	xsd:dateTime (optional time zone offset)			
	xsd:dateTimeStamp (required time zone offset)			
XML Literals	rdf:XMLLiteral			

Properties

Datatype properties: properties for which the value is a data literal

Object properties: properties for which the value is an individual

PPSR CCM V2 property name	Domain	Range	Profile	Multiplicity	Change with respect to PPSR CCM V1	Argumentation for the change
contains	ProjectExtent	ProjectExtent	Project geography	0..*	New property.	Added to be able to associate a spatial extent with its sub-extends.
describes	ProjectRecord	Project	Project.Metadata	0..*	New property.	Implicit property before.
hasAim	Project	Aim	Project.DetailedInformation	0..*	Adapted to the newly modeled semantics. No conceptual change.	See on the left.
hasCentroid	Polygon	Point	Project geography	0..1	Adapted to the newly modeled semantics. No conceptual change.	See on the left.
hasCode	AdministrativeUnit	AdministrativeUnitCode	Project geography	0..*	New property.	Added to be able to associate an administrative unit with its code.
hasContactPoint	Project	ContactPoint	Project contact point	0..*	Adapted to the newly modeled semantics. No conceptual change.	See on the left.
hasContactDetails	ContactPoint,	ContactDetail	Project contact point	0..*	Adapted to the newly	See on the left.

COST Action CA15212

Citizen Science to promote creativity, scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe

WG5 - Deliverable 1: Citizen-science ontology

	MeansOfContact	s			modeled semantics. No conceptual change.	
hasContactPointType	ContactPoint	ContactPointType	Project contact point	0..*	New property.	It allows more details to be modelled in the contact point.
hasCreationDate	ProjectRecord	DateCreated	Project.Metadata	0..1	No change.	See on the left.
hasCredit	Image	ImageCredit	Project.DetailedDescription.Image	0..1	Adapted to the newly modeled semantics. No conceptual change. This is also a property of Logo by inheritance.	See on the left.
hasDescription	FundingProgram	Description	Project funding	0..*	No change.	See on the left.
hasDescription	Project	Description	Project.Core	0..*	No change.	See on the left.
hasDuration	Project	Duration	Project.Core	0..1	New property.	It allows to directly model the duration of a project.
hasEndDate	Project	EndDate	Project.Core	0..1	No change.	See on the left.
hasExternalIdentifier	ProjectRecord	ExternalID	Project.Metadata	0..*	No change.	See on the left.
hasFundingProgram	Project	FundingProgram	Project funding	0..*	Implicit property before.	See on the left.
hasFundingSource	FundingProgram	FundingSource	Project funding	0..*	Implicit property before.	See on the left.

hasGeographicExtent	Project	GeographicExtent	Project geography	0..*	We separated a project's "GeographicExtent" from its "SpatialAreaOfInterest". The former can be used to represent the partners or participants locations, whereas the latter is the area on which the project operates.	See on the left.
hasIdentifier	FundingProgram	GUID	Project funding	0..1	No change.	See on the left.
hasIdentifier	Project	GUID	Project.Core	0..1	No change.	See on the left.
hasIdentifier	ProjectRecord	GUID	Project.Metadata	0..1	No change.	See on the left.
hasImage	Project	Image	Project.DetailedInformation.Image	0..*	No change.	See on the left.
hasKeyword	Project	Keyword	Project.DetailedInformation	0..*	No change.	See on the left.
hasNaturalLanguage	ProjectRecord	Language	Project.Metadata	0..*	New property.	It allows to model the association between the record and a human-readable natural language in which it is written.
hasLatitude	Point	Latitude	Project geography	0..1	No change.	See on the left.
hasLongitude	Point	Longitude	Project geography	0..1	No change.	See on the left.

COST Action CA15212

Citizen Science to promote creativity, scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe

WG5 - Deliverable 1: Citizen-science ontology

hasMeansOfContact	ContactPoint	MeansOfContact	Project contact point	0..*	New property.	It allows to model different means of contact, such as email or phone.
hasName	FundingProgram	Name	Project funding	0..*	No change.	See on the left.
hasName	FundingSource	Name	Project funding	0..*	No change.	See on the left.
hasName	Project	Name	Project.Core	0..*	No change.	See on the left.
hasName	SpatialExtent	Name	Project geography	0..*	It was "Project location".	Part of larger model restructuring.
hasOrigin	ProjectRecord	Origin	Project.Metadata	0..*	No change.	See on the left.
hasOutcome	Project	Outcome	Project.DetailedInformation	0..*	New property.	It allows to model the real outcome of a project, besides the intended outcome.
hasSpatialAreaOfInterest	Project	SpatialAreaOfInterest	Project geography	0..*	We separated a project's "GeographicExtent" from its "SpatialAreaOfInterest". The former can be used to represent the partners or participants locations, whereas the latter is the area on which the project operates.	As this might be out in space, we speak about "SpatialAreaOfInterest" (i.e. non necessarily geography).
hasSpatialExtent	SpatialAreaOfInt	SpatialExtent	Project geography	0..*	New property.	Adaptation of existing

COST Action CA15212

Citizen Science to promote creativity, scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe

WG5 - Deliverable 1: Citizen-science ontology

	erest					properties to the newly modeled semantics.
hasStartDate	Project	StartDate	Project.Core	0..1	No change.	See on the left.
hasStatus	Project	Status	Project.Core	0..1	No change.	See on the left.
hasTag	Project	Tag	Project.DetailedInformation	0..*	No change.	See on the left.
hasAdministrativeUnitType	AdministrativeUnit	AdministrativeUnitType	Project geography	0..*	New property.	Generalisation of existing property.
hasContactPointType	ContactPoint	ContactPointType	Project.Affiliation	0..*	New property.	It allows to model different kinds of contact points.
hasFundingSourceType	FundingSource	FundingSourceType	Project funding	0..*	New property.	Generalisation. Adding "FundingSource", the model has a more robust structure that holds beyond US federal sponsoring.
hasWebPage	Project	WebPage	Project.Core	0..*	No change.	
wasLastUpdated	ProjectRecord	DateUpdated	Project.Metadata	0..1	No change.	

Classes

In the following table, all classes of the ontology are presented in alphabetical order.

In a generalisation effort, we decided to speak of “Name” instead of “ProjectName”, “URL” instead of “ProjectURL”, etc. Whereas this is perfectly clear in a graph-based representation where the link between, for example, “project” and “name” is shown, it might add confusion in a table-based view.

PPSR CCM V2 class name	PPSR CCM V2 database name	Universal data type - if applicable	Subclasses	Properties	Description/ comments	Change with respect to PPSR CCM V1	Argumentation for the change
Administrative unit	AdministrativeUnit	-	-	hasAdministrativeUnitType hasCode	We introduce possible separations of different types of administrative units. Each “AdministrativeUnit” can then have a name (via GeographicExtent), a type and a code.	New class.	Was implicit before.
Administrative unit code	AdministrativeUnitCode	Strings	-	-	Examples: 009, IT.	New class.	Was implicit before. Good way to uniquely identify administrative units.
Administrative unit type	AdministrativeUnitType	-	-	-	Examples: UNRegion, NUTS (Level 1).	Generalised from “UN regions”.	Applicability to more cases.

COST Action CA15212

Citizen Science to promote creativity,
scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe

WG5 - Deliverable 1: Citizen-science ontology

Aim	Aim	-	-	hasIntendedOutcome	Primary aim, goal or objective. [Source: PPSR-Core].	Changed from a datatype to a class.	Making it explicit that a project intended outcomes relates to a particular aim.
Contact details	ContactDetails	Strings	-	-	Holding the actual contact information. Data type could depend on the MeansOfContact.	Generalised from email in PPSR-Core V1.	Acknowledging multiple possibilities of contacting people.
Contact point	ContactPoint	-	-	hasContactDetails hasContactPointType hasMeansOfContact	Can serve as contact point for different purposes.	New class.	Was implicit before.
Contact point type	ContactPointType	controlled vocabulary	-	-	Separating, for example the communication contact point for a project from the financial contact point (can also be used for a data set).	New class to also account for the separation between project partners and project hosts.	Need to indicate different kind of contact points e.g. for a project or project host.
Date created	DateCreated	Time Instants	-	-	DateCreated depends on DateUpdated. (It cannot be later.)	New class.	Was implicit before. We tried to standardise the datatypes used.

COST Action CA15212

Citizen Science to promote creativity,
scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe

WG5 - Deliverable 1: Citizen-science ontology

Date updated	DateUpdated	Time Instants	-	-	DateUpdated depends on DateCreated. (It cannot be earlier.)	New class.	Was implicit before. We tried to standardise the datatypes used.
Description	Description	Strings	-	-	Brief statement explaining the core characteristics of the project.	New class.	Was implicit before. We tried to standardise the datatypes used.
Duration	Duration	Numbers	-	-	Duration in months. It can be calculated via StartDate and EndDate.	New class.	Alternative information to end date that frequently occurs in proprietary project metadata.
End date	EndDate	Time Instants	-	-	Data on which the project ends or ended.	New class.	Was implicit before. We tried to standardise the datatypes used.
External ID	ExternalID	Strings	-	-	The identifier of the project in an external database or repository. [Source: PPSR-Core]	Field of PPSR-Core with new name.	We tried to standardise the datatypes used. The name was changed in order to enable the use of this field in other contexts.
Funding program	FundingProgram	-	-	hasDescription	Indication of the	New class.	Implicit concept

COST Action CA15212

Citizen Science to promote creativity, scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe

WG5 - Deliverable 1: Citizen-science ontology

				hasFundingSource hasIdentifier hasName	program that funds or funded a project.		before.
Funding source	FundingSource	-	-	hasFundingSource Type hasName	Sponsor(s) of the project.	New class.	Separation of the property "USFederalSponsor" into two more generic properties of the class "FundingSource" ("Name" and "FundingSourceType"). Adding "FundingSource", the model has a more robust structure that holds beyond US federal sponsoring. Added EU and US examples for illustration.
Funding source type	FundingSourceType	-	-	-	Examples: US federal sponsor, EU sponsor.	New class.	Separation of the property "USFederalSponsor" into two more generic properties of the class "FundingSource" ("Name" and "FundingSourceType").

Geographic extent	GeographicExtent	-	AdministrativeUnit	-	We separated a project's "GeographicExtent" from its "SpatialAreaOfInterest". The former can be used to represent the partners or participants locations, whereas the latter is the area on which the project operates.	New class.	Implicit class before. Need to be more explicit about the intended meaning of the term.
Geometry	Geometry	-	Point Polygon	-	We use a common way of modelling geometric representations of spatial objects. We particularly account for point geometries (for the time being with two standard coordinates) and for polygon geometries, which have a point in their center.	New class.	More refined modelling of project geography
GUID	GUID	Strings	-	-	Globally unique identifier.	New class.	Implicit class before. We tried to standardise the

COST Action CA15212

Citizen Science to promote creativity,
scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe

WG5 - Deliverable 1: Citizen-science ontology

							datatypes used.
Image	Image	-	Logo	hasImageCredit	Such an image from a project can be anything.	Used as a superclass of logo.	Need for clarifying the type of image, esp. indicating if this is a project logo.
Image credit	ImageCredit	Strings	-	-	Acknowledging the person who did or provided the picture.	New class.	Implicit class before.
Intended outcome	IntendedOutcome	controlled vocabulary (from PPSR CCM V1)	-	-	A project's goals, or intended outcomes of participation. [Source: PPSR-Core]	Renamed from PPSR-Core "Intended outcomes" for consistency.	Just used singular instead of plural.
Keyword	Keyword	Strings	-	-	Keywords (comma separated), which are indexed and aid in searching for and finding projects. [Source: PPSR-Core]	Renamed from PPSR-Core "Keywords" for consistency.	Just used singular instead of plural.
Language	Language	controlled vocabulary	-	-	A system of communication used by a particular country or	New class.	The natural language of the project record is important because it can affect reuse

COST Action CA15212

Citizen Science to promote creativity, scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe

WG5 - Deliverable 1: Citizen-science ontology

					community. [source:https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/language]		and sharing.
Latitude	Latitude	-	-	-	Part of a WGS84 coordinate, with Longitude.	New class.	Implicit class before.
Logo	Logo	-	-	-	Here we want to specifically say that this is the logo of the project.	New class.	Project logos are a core part of project representations in catalogues.
Longitude	Longitude	-	-	-	Part of a WGS84 coordinate, with Latitude.	New class.	Implicit class before.
Means of contact	MeansOfContact	controlled vocabulary	-	-	Separating email from phone number, twitter handle, etc.	New class.	Acknowledge multiple possibilities to address a contact point.
Name	Name	Strings	-	-	Examples: NASA, NSF, UE.	New class.	Implicit class before.
Origin	Origin	Strings	-	-	The name of the project database where a project was first registered. Allows traceability of a project in multiple databases	Field of PPSR-Core with new name.	We tried to standardise the datatypes used. The name was changed in order to enable the use of this field in other contexts.

COST Action CA15212

Citizen Science to promote creativity, scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe

WG5 - Deliverable 1: Citizen-science ontology

					to its original registration. [Source: PPSR-Core]		
Outcome	Outcome	-	-	-	It represents the actual outcomes of a project.	New class.	It has been added to allow representing the actual outcomes of a project, which are not necessarily the "intended outcomes".
Point	Point	-	-	hasLatitude hasLongitude	Representing locations in their most simple form.	New class.	Implicit class before.
Polygon	Polygon	-	-	hasCentroid	Possibility to represent locations of areal nature.	New class.	Implicit class before.
Project	Project	-	-	hasAim hasContactPoint hasDescription hasDuration hasEndDate hasFundingProgram hasGeographicExtent hasIdentifier hasImage hasKeyword	A collaborative effort of citizen science, for example to report observations on particular targets (domains or locations).	New class.	Implicit class before.

				<p>hasOutcome hasProjectRecord hasName hasSpatialAreaOfInterest hasStartDate hasStatus hasTag hasWebPage isIllustratedBy</p>			
Project record	ProjectRecord	-	-	<p>hasCreationDate hasExternalIdentifier hasIdentifier wasLastUpdated describes hasNaturalLanguage hasOrigin</p>	A concrete documentation of a project's characteristics, in a repository of some sort such as an online database.	New class.	Implicit concept before, only as a sub-heading in the table "Database information".
Spatial area of interest	SpatialAreaOfInterest	-	-	<p>hasSpatialExtent</p>	Representation of the spatial extent addressed by the project, can be on earth, the moon, etc.	New class.	We separated a project's "GeographicExtent" from its "SpatialAreaOfInterest". The former can be used to represent the partners or participants locations, whereas the latter is

COST Action CA15212

Citizen Science to promote creativity,
scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe

WG5 - Deliverable 1: Citizen-science ontology

							the area on which the project operates.
Spatial extent	SpatialExtent	-	Geographic Extent	contains hasGeometry hasName	Principle class to capture any spatial extent in the model, for example used to describe the geographic coverage of a project.	New class.	Implicit concept before.
Start date	StartDate	Time Instants	-	-		New class.	Was implicit before. We tried to standardise the datatypes used.
Status	Status	controlled vocabulary	-	-	It can be calculated via StartDate and EndDate.	New class.	Was implicit before.
Tag	Tag	controlled vocabulary	-	-	Controlled vocabulary terms, supplied by the person who entered the project, to assist with search and filtering. [Source: PPSR-Core]	Renamed from PPSR-Core "Tags" for consistency.	Just used singular instead of plural.
Topic	Topic	controlled vocabulary	-	-	The project topic or field of science.	Renamed from PPSR-	We tried to standardise the

COST Action CA15212

Citizen Science to promote creativity, scientific literacy, and innovation throughout Europe

WG5 - Deliverable 1: Citizen-science ontology

					[Source: PPSR-Core]	Core "Project topic" for consistency.	datatypes used. The name was changed in order to enable the use of this field in other contexts.
Web page	WebPage	IRIs	-	-		Renamed from URL.	URL is the data type but here it is important to note that this particular URL represents the web page of the project.